

EFFECT OF UV/VISIBLE LASER IRRADIATION ON SOME HYBRID FORMULATIONS CONTAINING PHOTOREACTIVE URETHANE (DI)METHACRYLATES AND GRAPHENE

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ABSTRACT

A series of photopolymerizable composites based on urethane monomers, macromers and graphene or graphene-Ag has been synthesized by using UV/vis irradiation or femtosecond laser beam. The structural characterization, graphene's morphology and the properties of materials have been achieved through ¹H NMR and FTIR spectroscopies, optical microscopy, TEM, and SEM/EDAX analysis. The photopolymerization of urethane acrylic monomers containing morpholine, bornyl or siloxane moieties in structure (20 wt.%) taken in combination with other urethane dimethacrylates (80 wt.%) in the absence and the presence of small quantities of graphene/graphene-Ag and Irgacure 819 as photoinitiator was investigated by FT-IR. The photopolymerization experiments revealed a good photoreactivity of the monomer mixtures (DC: 86-98%) after 5 min exposure to irradiation and the incorporation of graphene-Ag (0.1 wt.%) led to a decrease of the degree of conversion (~80%). In the pure formulations the polymerization rate varied between $1.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $4.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, while in the corresponding hybrids this parameter had a value around $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Moreover, two-photon photopolymerization of the same formulations with and without graphene allowed the formation of 2D microstructures by direct laser writing procedure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, the nanoscience field plays a crucial role in nanotechnology, especially in areas such computing, sensors, photonics, biomedical and other modern applications. The discovery of graphene with its remarkable physicochemical properties and ability to be dispersed in various polymeric matrices has generated a novel class of polymer nanocomposites with high potential for improving electrical, thermal, mechanical and gas barrier properties of the resulted graphene/polymer nanocomposites even at small loading. Typically, graphene is a two-dimensional sheet composed of sp² carbon atoms arranged in a honeycomb structure that can be viewed as the building block of other graphitic carbon allotropes (fullerenes, nanotubes, graphite) of different sizes [1-3]. For instance, graphite (3D carbon structure) can be made of graphene sheets stacked on top of each other, while the preparation of fullerenes (0D carbon allotrope) and carbon nanotubes (1D carbon allotrope) involves

wrapping graphene sheets and rolling and slicing graphene sheets, respectively. In fact, these allotrope forms are not yielded from graphene. Graphite is a natural product, and carbon nanotubes were obtained in 1991 following the discovery of fullerene in 1985 [4]. Although the first graphene nanosheets were reported over 30 years before, isolation of single layer of graphene was performed in 2004, when graphene was separated from graphite through micromechanical cleavage [5]. As demonstrated, graphene sheets have a large set of unusual properties as thermal conductivity, mechanical stiffness, fracture strength and special electronic transport properties, for which reason the uniform dispersion of graphene nanosheets within a polymer matrix continue to be of great interest and needs a deep investigation. However, in order to avoid the agglomeration of graphene sheets caused by Van der Waals interactions, the achievement of a better exfoliation of the nanosheets in the organic phase is essential for the exploitation of the graphene-based materials. More accurately, these requirements imply surface reactions that assume a covalent attachment to graphene by means of different linkages like ester, amide and the others [6,7], but all the specific properties depend on the distribution of graphene layers inside the polymer composite and on the control of interfacial linkage between the graphene and the organic matrix.

One specific branch of this research has been focused on the study of graphene oxide (GO) considered as a precursor for the graphene synthesis that use chemical/thermal reduction processes of graphite, with consequent dispersion and exfoliation in water or organic solvents [2]. As results, the GO-based materials have become popular, at least with respect to electrochemical and optical applications, when they incorporated electroactive or sensitive species.

Among the strategies used for preparing GO-based polymer composites, the photocuring methods received an increasing importance, the most suitable candidates for the photopolymerization processes being the (meth)acrylate systems, which upon their exposure to UV/visible light at room temperature and in the absence of each solvent ("green" chemistry) lead to eco-friendly hybrid networks for applications in coatings technology (electromagnetic shielding/antistatic materials). Additionally, two-photon polymerization (2PP) induced with a femtosecond laser proved to be an attractive way of photopolymerization, which allows the creation of 2D and 3D micro/nanostructures with variable geometry. In the light of these considerations, we synthesized novel urethane monomers with morpholine, bornyl or siloxane units in structure to be used in reactive monomer mixtures for preparing graphene/poly(urethane acrylates) composites through UV photopolymerization or direct laser writing process by femtosecond laser pulse visible-light beams. Photopolymerization kinetics together with some properties of the derived hybrid films is reported.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and characterization

Benzophenone-3,3',4,4'-tetracarboxylic dianhydride, 2-hydroxyethyl methacrylate (HEMA), 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate, poly(ethylene oxide) (PEG, $M_w = 400 \text{ g mol}^{-1}$), poli(tetrametilen oxid) de masa moleculara 1000 (DMA-PTHF), 1,6-diisocyanato-2,2,4-trimethylhexane were purchased from Sigma Aldrich Chemical Co. and used without further purification. The initiator used was 2-dimethylamino-2-(4-methyl-benzyl)-1-(4-morpholin-4-yl-phenyl)-butan-1-one (Irgacure 819) from Ciba and graphite powder from Oltchim-Ramnicu Valcea, Romania ($>600 \mu\text{m}$, with 99,9 % C). Graphenes were prepared by modified Hummer's Offeman's method, and from GO by thermal treatment at $1000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively from graphite powder [8].

The structure of compounds was verified by $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and FTIR spectroscopy using a Bruker 400 MHz spectrometer and a Specord M80, respectively. For FTIR kinetics, the samples were exposed to UV/vis irradiation using a LA 500 device ($\lambda = 450\text{-}500 \text{ nm}$) at room temperature. The morphology of the films was investigated using optical microscopy (LEICA DM 2500M), scanning electron microscopy (Tesla BS 301), and TEM measurements (Hitachi High-Tech HT7700 microscope with an accelerating voltage of 100 kV). The set-up for 2PP experiments is a home-made Direct Laser Writing (DLW) workstation coupled with a Clark CPA-2010 amplified femtosecond laser working at a wavelength of 775 nm, having pulse duration of 200 fs and a repetition rate of 2 kHz. The solutions in tetrahydrofuran were placed on a XYZ motion stage with stepper motors and piezodriver. The laser

beam was moved on the sample using galvanic mirrors. A Z translation stage and a visualization system with CCD camera are used for precisely positioning the sample in the plane of the focused laser. Finally, the polymerized samples were washed with isopropyl alcohol.

2.2. Synthesis

Adding of 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate at poly(dimethylsiloxane-bis(hydroxyalkyl)) or at 2-borneol led to the obtaining of siloxane macromer (UDMA-Si) and bornyl methacrylate (UMA-Bo) respectively. The preparation of 2-N-morpholinoethyl methacrylate (UMA-Mo) involved a reaction between 3-morpholinopropylamine and salicylic aldehyde followed by the reaction of the formed product in the first step with 2-isocyanatoethyl methacrylate. The addition reaction of hydroxyl group to isocyanate group was followed by FTIR spectroscopy up to the disappearance of the absorption band of the isocyanate group from the spectrum.

UMA-Mo, ¹H NMR in CDCl₃ (δ, ppm): 8.3 (CH=N), 6.8-7.4(Ar-H), 6.01 si 5.6 (CH₂=C), 4.2-4.5 (CH₂-OCO), 3.69-3.62 (CH₂-O from morpholine), 3.53 (CH₂-N=), 3.5 (CH₂-NH), 2.4 (CH₂-N from morpholine), 1.93 (CH₃ from methacrylate); UDMA-Si, ¹H NMR in CDCl₃ (δ, ppm): 6.1 si 5.0 (CH₂=C), 4.1 (CH₂-OCO), 3.35 (CH₂-NH-CO), 0.02 (CH₃-Si). UMA-Bo, ¹H NMR in CDCl₃ (δ, ppm): 6.14 si 5.6 (CH₂=C-), 5.0 (NH), 4.85 (CH-OCO), 4.25 (CH₂-O-CO), 3.5 (CH₂-NH-COO), 1.93 (CH₂ from methacrylate), 1.88, 1.73, 1.35 si 1.2 (CH₂, CH from bornyl), 0.9 (CH₃ from bornyl);

The dimethacrylates with benzophenone and poly(ethylene oxide) segment (DMA-BP400) in structure or with poly(tetramethylene oxide) (DMA-PTHF) were prepared according to previously reported methods [9, 10].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Characterization of filler

The morphology and structure of the graphene LGF2 used in our study were investigated through FTIR spectroscopy and TEM investigation. As shown in Figure 1, the FT-IR spectrum of LGF2 revealed the presence of different type of oxygen functionalities with specific bands corresponding to the O-H stretching vibrations (3400 cm⁻¹), stretching vibrations from C=O (1720 cm⁻¹), and C-O unit absorption (1060 cm⁻¹). In the case of graphene-Ag (GF1Ag1, GF1Ag0.5) a shift accompanied of a decrease of the absorption band intensity of the hydroxyl group together with a variation of the CO bands can be identified.

From the TEM image of LGF2 sample it can visualize a stratified structure of graphene sheets, while the same analysis of GF1-Ag1 suggests a relatively uniform dispersion of Ag nanoparticles with size between 15 and 20 nm on the surface of graphene, without neglecting the presence of unattached metal nanoparticles or free nanoparticles.

Figure 1: FTIR spectra of graphenes used in photopolymerization experiments (a) and TEM images for LGF2 (b) and GF1Ag1 (c)

3.2. Photopolymerization study

In order to prepare some hybrid composites based on the above described graphenes, we synthesized three urethane acrylates containing morpholino (UMO-MO), bornyl (UMO-Bo) or siloxane units (UDMA-Si) in structure to be used in photopolymerizable formulations besides other urethane dimethacrylates of oligomer type with good-film forming properties (DMA-BP400; DMA-PTHF) taken as co-monomers. Structures of all these monomer/macromers are presented in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Structures of urethane acrylates/dimethacrylates used in our study.

The aim of this work being the preparation of graphene/polymer photopolymerizable composites firstly we evaluated the photopolymerization kinetics of the formulations containing the synthesized monomers taken in mixture with DMA-BP400 or DMA-PTHF (20:80 gravimetric ratio) as co-monomers using FTIR analysis. Consequently, the double bond conversion (DC) to single bonds after polymerization was determined at room temperature in the presence of Irgacure 819 (2%) as the photoinitiator. Figure 2 displays plots of the photopolymerization process with irradiation time for the formulation based on UMO-Mo/DMA-PTHF under UV/vis light (10 mW/cm^2) along with the double bond conversion versus irradiation time for the formulations investigated, when a degree of conversion between 86 and 98% was found after 5 min of irradiation of the samples. In the FTIR spectra a decrease of the absorption band located at $\sim 816 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and assigned to the photopolymerizable groups with irradiation time was evidenced. Moreover, the maximum of polymerization rate attained values in the field $1.4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ - $4.7 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, the higher value being determined for the mixture UDMA-Bo/DMA-BP400 (Fig. 3).

Figure 2: Spectral changes in the formulation UMO-Mo/DMA-PTHF during UV irradiation (a) and the degree of conversion of double bonds (b)

By incorporating 0.1 graphene-Ag (GF₁Ag₁) the degree of conversion decreased at about 80%, and the polymerization rate is diminished at $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. From these results we can conclude that the polymerization of the monomers under an intense radiation could be favored.

Figure 3: Evolution of the maximum polymerization rate for all formulations upon UV irradiation (determined from FTIR spectra).

Monitoring the photopolymerized films through ATR-FTIR it is obvious that the absorption bands of acrylic functions disappeared from the spectrum, and other absorption bands were easily shifted compared to the pure oligodimethacrylate DMA-BP₄₀₀ (Fig. 4).

Figure 4: FTIR spectra of the polymer films based on DMA-BP₄₀₀ alone and in mixture with UMA-Bo, UMA-Mo or UDMA-Si.

EDAX analysis of the polymer film containing UMA-Mo/DMA-BP400 suggested a specific composition of constituent elements with atomic percentage of 80.39% C, 3.66% O and 15.96% N (Fig. 5). In the case of hybrid films with 1% LGF2 or 0.1% GF₁Ag₁ in composition, the EDAX spectra indicated the presence of the same elements with a small modification of the atomic ratio in function of the filler loading (Fig. 5, b, c).

Figure 5: EDAX results of the polymer film (a) and hybrid films (b, c).

Next, the thermal properties of the polymer films and their hybrids were also examined through thermogravimetric analysis (ATG). The registered data have shown that the decomposition process occurs in three well-defined steps. From the Figure 6a it can appreciate that the first step of decomposition is estimated to be in the range 220-380 °C, with a weight loss between 42 and 50 %. It become evident that the second step of decomposition (380-530 °C) yielded a weight loss around 70%, the proces continuing with complete degradation of the polymer network.

By TEM analysis of the hybrid composite resulted from UMA-Mo/DMA-BP400 with 0.1 % GF₁Ag₁ (Fig. 6b) the existence of graphene thin sheets in the organic matrix besides agglomerates of Ag nanoparticles with size over 100 nm is confirmed.

Figure 6: ATG curves for films based on 80% DMA-BP₄₀₀ and 20% UMA-Bo (UMA-Mo, UDMA-Si) or DMA-BP₄₀₀/UMA-Mo and 1% LGF2 or 0.1% GF₁Ag₁ (a). TEM image for hybrid composite DMA-BP₄₀₀/UMA-Mo with 0.1% GF₁Ag₁ (b).

Based on this information, some of these formulations were exposed to femtosecond laser pulses (λ : 775 nm) to create polymer structures that can be visualized by optical microscopy and SEM. For 2PP experiments we used the formulations UMA-Mo/DMA-PTHF, UMA-Bo/DMA-BP400, UMA-Si/DMA-PTHF or only DMP-BP400 with and without graphene, when grids of 20x20 lines systems with distance between lines of 100 μ m were built on glass substrates at different incident laser powers and a scanning velocity of 3 mm/s. Table 1 presents optical microscopy images for the grid microstructures processed at two laser powers (3 and 5 mW). In the case of some of them we can observe the generation of well-defined structures with no influence of laser power, and a good efficiency of the developing procedure, the nonirradiated regions being completely cleaned. A

comparable construction was processed for the formulation based on a single macromer DMP-BP400, but in this case, yielding of regular photocured grids depends on the incident laser power and the thickness of the lines corresponding to the 2D structures varied from few microns up to 20 μm .

Formulation	Laser parameters	Without graphene	With LGF2 graphene (0.02%)
UMA-Mo/DMA-PTHF (20:80)	P= 3 W Vs = 1mm/s Δ =100 μm		
UMA-Bo/DMA-BP400 (20:80)	P= 3 W Vs = 1mm/s Δ =100 μm		
UMA-Si/DMA-PTHF (20:80)	P= 3 W Vs = 1mm/s Δ =100 μm		
DMP-BP400	P= 5 W Vs = 1 mm/s Δ =100 μm		

Table 1: Optical microscopy images obtained with our formulations subjected to femtosecond laser pulses (2 PP).

Figure 7 shows the optical microscopy (MO) and SEM images for the grid microstructures generated from UMA-Mo/DMA-PTHF with 0.05 % LGF2 (a, e), 0.05 % GF_1Ag_1 (b, f), 0.05 % $\text{GF}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (c, g), and 0.1 % $\text{GF}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (d, h), a better clarity being observed in the hybrid composite that contain non-functionalized graphene.

Figure 7: MO and SEM images for the films based on UMA-Mo/DMA-PTHF with 0.05% LGF2 (a, e), 0.05% GF_1Ag_1 (b, f), 0.05% $\text{GF}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (c, g), 0.1% $\text{GF}_1\text{Ag}_{0.5}$ (d, h); (scale bar 200 μm).

As can be seen, there are many images that suggest that the microstructured grids performed in the absence/ presence of 0.02 and 0.05 wt.% graphene have no visible defects and presented a good developing procedure to remove the nonirradiated region. Therefore, 2D structures with thickness of the polymerized lines between few microns and 20 μm follows to be extended to 3D structures based on our hybrid combinations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Some urethane methacrylates were used in monomer mixtures besides flexible urethane oligodimethacrylates and photopolymerized under UV/ vis exposure and femtosecond laser pulses (2PP) in presence/absence of graphene/graphene-Ag, the photoreactivity being affected by filler loading. By using 2PP procedure 2D photopolymerized structures with thickness of the polymerized lines under 20 μm were also created.

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